

BABUR IN THE INTERPRETATION OF HEROLD LAMB

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ABSTRACT

In the 30s of the last century, the great American writer Herold Lamb appeared in the field of literature. Unlike his pen-pals, he created works of art about the great figures of the Eastern Renaissance. However, the life and work of this talented writer were little studied in Uzbekistan during the Soviet era, and in the former Soviet Union in general. He devoted his adult life to the study of the cultural history of Asia, Russia, and the Middle East.

The artist began his literary career with the New York Times. H. Lamb has made great strides in journalism. Arthur Hoffman, the magazine's editor-in-chief, allowed the prospective writer to write articles on a topic of his choice. Special mention should be made of the journalist's novel "Temur, which shook the world", published in New York in 1928. At the beginning of the twentieth century, for the first time in American literature, the writer created a natural, vital image of the great Sahibkiran, which fully reflects all the achievements and shortcomings. The image of Timur, created by H. Lamb, is presented to the reader as a kind man who gave good military education to his children and grandchildren. Sahibkiran Immortal's ideas are first of all his great "architect", his ideas are vividly reflected in the pages of the work, in the

words of the author, "his epic written in stone". The gardens created by Amir Temur amaze the writer. Among American writers, H. Lamb was not the first to describe Central Asia as an incomprehensible region or a "dark" page in the history of the East. the famous East, which nurtured scientists, is seen as a country of Renaissance civilization. Emphasizing the greatness of Sahibkiran's contribution to the world's cultural heritage, the writer concludes that the emergence of great personalities like Timur in the Eastern "Renaissance" is a historical necessity. From ancient times, Uzbek classics have earned the respect and admiration of Western readers and intellectuals. Alisher Navoi and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur became the leading representatives of world literature, raising Uzbek classical literature to the level of

masterpieces of the world. Since the 17th century, Babur's works have been reprinted several times in many European languages. Much has been written about them. The twentieth century is important for us. Because during this time, Babur's works were translated into the Americas. Along with articles and reviews, the author's work "Bobur - Tiger" was created in the United States. The book was published in 1961 in New York.

The author's works can be added to the style of the autobiographical genre, widely used in the United States. Of all the types of fiction and biographical narratives, biographical novels are the most important. What genre can it be? In our opinion, to find an answer to this question, it is necessary to turn to A. Morua, who is not only a famous master of this genre but also a theoretical founder. In his lectures at the University of Cambridge, he considered biographical novels to be a separate, independent, genre of art and science, such as essays.

An artistic biography describes various aspects of a particular historical figure that are sufficiently well known. These images should always be presented on a scientific basis. Thus, this artistic biography becomes the main criterion of the novel genre. In such novels, the life of the protagonist is usually covered. Fiction biographies require that life be expressed through the character of a historical figure. Like all other works of art, biographical fiction novels help the reader to understand the social nature of society, ideological and moral issues, and the events that stirred humanity at one time or another.

It will be aimed at revealing the moral characteristics of the heroes of the biographical art genre while maintaining its

scientific and educational significance. In evaluating their actions and morals, the writer must be honest and fair. That is why the ideological and moral position of the creator is very important. The author of a biographical work has a very big and responsible task in creating an artistic image of a historical figure. "Literary genre-biographical novels emerge at the intersection of two paths: psychological novels and historical research. The main problem for the author is that the scientific approach to artistic methods, the art is "light as a rainbow." That's when a writer's talent comes into play. There is a harmony between the work of H. Lamb and the books of the master of the biographical genre Irving Stone.

This book about Babur consists of an introduction and eight chapters. During the creation of the work, H. Lamb visited Tashkent and talked with prominent orientalists, academician VV Bartold, prof. He studied the works of S. Azimjanova and other orientalists. The structure of the book, the division into chapters is reminiscent of the order in the "Baburname". The author relies entirely on Babur's work, in which he quotes a few pages in some places and then comments on the rest of the story. When we compared these passages with the original Uzbek version of the Baburname, we found that they were mostly translated into English.

The work begins with the story of Babur's struggle and retreat from Shaybani Khan. Subsequent chapters are devoted to Babur's conquest of India and the establishment of the Great Empire.

In the last eight chapters of the book "Bobur - Tiger", the foundation of the Great Baburid Empire in India is described in vivid scenes

of Babur's life in India. H. Lamb expresses the positive aspects of Babur Mirza during his rule in the novel with the following lines: "With him he brought to India the Timurid devotion to music and verse – and wine. His fondness for building gardens in the most unlikely spots earned him the name of the Gardener King. More than tree-shaded gardens followed him to Agra. Out of white and red stone, palace dwellings, great mosques, and tombs began to rise in the pathway of the moguls. Babur hardly lived to see it, but Samarkand, his lost city, was brought to India".

Thus, Babur brought his beloved city of Samarkand to India.

At the end of the work, the author gives an objective assessment of the work done by Babur Mirza.

H. Lamb tries to give a fair assessment of Babur's work in the play:

"The Tiger had torn the map of India apart, across the old mountain barriers, joining Kabul and Kashmir to the Punjab rivers and the Ganges basin, and ended, in so doing, the feudal hegemonies of the Lodi sultans and Rajput princes, and religious conflict as well. He restored the power of a single monarch, long absent in Indian lands. His dominion had a new outlook, toward the future rather than the past. Local traditions and economies were preserved.

Government, however, came, into the hands of the ministers of the throne. The monarch remained aloof, to judge the conduct of his administrators. His subject could appeal to him as judge against his own government". In his last words, the author dwells on some events after Babur's death, his burial, Babur's tomb, and some changes in the history of recent Asia. As a great master of words, Babur paid great attention to correct spelling, fluent style, and pronunciation.

In the summer of 1960, H. Lamb visited the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in Tashkent. The author's novels on the history of the East, in particular, about Amir Temur and Babur, are of great importance to us. It should be noted that the author's works were banned in the former Soviet Union. They have not been translated or published.

Conclusion: The work of Herold Lamb, in particular, his biographical novels dedicated to the great figures of the Eastern Renaissance - Amir Temur, the great king, and poet Babur Mirzo, as well as Umar Khayyam, is rarely studied by our literary critics. A study of this author's works on Uzbekistan in general, on the subject of the East, shows that the interest in our heritage in the West is several times stronger than we have ever imagined.

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